

The Preacher and the Plague

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We are living a fatal plague, we do not know who will come out of it. Albert Camus published *The Plague* in June 1947, three years after the liberation of Paris from the Nazi occupation. The Plague (TP) is the tale of a natural calamity that descends on the Algerian town of Oran. Evil is the plague in the soul of man which continues pecking the liver of any man as in the case of Prometheus. I have locked up myself in the library of the University of Leuven to understand and defend God from the complicity of evil which was a problem of highest concern for me. In the aforesaid novel, Tarou while narrating the story of his life to Dr Rieux, tells: “I know positively ... that each of us has the plague within him; no one, no one on earth, is free from it. And I know, too, that we must keep endless watch on ourselves lest in a careless movement we breathe in somebody’s face and fasten the infection on him. What’s natural is the microbe. All the rest – health, integrity, purity (if you like) – is a product of the human will, of a vigilance that must never falter. The good man, the man who infects hardly anyone, is the man who has the fewest lapses of attention. And it needs tremendous will-power, a never-ending attention of the mind, to avoid such lapses” (T.P. p. 207). This is exactly what happens today all over the world. The corona virus has lifted all our absolute laws of the Church and made them relative to man. Finally, we all realised with a short span of time that man does not live for Sabbath. The god-men within

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retreat centres of our Church went on conducting healing services while all possible and real diseases are made dumb and mute by the virus. There were lot of egoist pretensions not only in the religious fields but also in the positive sciences. All without any distinction – poor, rich, high class or low class – were made mere prey of the deadly virus.

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Father Paneloux of Camus’ novel is the learned Jesuit who sees the plague as the divine punishment dreaded by sinners. In spite of what divides the five characters of the novel they will work side by side for something that unites them ‘beyond blasphemy and prayers.’ The plague appears as the symbol of evil, as the fate’s weight on man, as death, as the symbol of life itself. The Plague can be read as the chronicle of an epidemic and as the symbol of human condition. Dr Rieux’s metaphysical rebellion reaches its apex in the novel. After witnessing impotently the long and cruel agony of the poor boy, together with Tarou and Fr Paneloux, Dr Rieux suddenly vents his rage on the Jesuit, who is asking him to love what he cannot understand. ‘Until my dying day,’ he retorted, ‘I shall refuse to love a scheme of things in which children are put to torture’ (TP, p. 178). Dr Rieux is terribly angry with Fr Paneloux for attempting to justify the suffering and death of human beings, to give evil a meaning and a *raison d’être*. The priest said that ‘there were some things we could grasp as touching God, and others we could not.’ Fr Paneloux was now walking, may be unsuspectingly, in the footsteps of metaphysical rebels. He became finally convinced, like Dr Rieux, that ‘it is not the suffering of a child which is repugnant

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in itself, but the fact that the suffering is not justified' (TP, p. 73). Fr Paneloux preached two sermons in the midst of the plague but the second significantly differed from the first. "He spoke in a gentler, more thoughtful tone than on the previous occasion, and several times was noticed to be stumbling over his words. A yet more noteworthy change was that instead of saying 'you' he now said 'we' (TP p. 182). The priest lies surrendered to death, reconciling with it, while the latter resisted it. 'I don't want to die, Tarrou said to Dr Rieux, and I shall put up a fight. But if I lose the match, I want to make a good end of it' (TP p. 231). Tarrou thus courageously fought death the same way as he resisted historical nihilism in the novel.

Fr. Paneloux fails to defend the divine from the complicity of evil, or his explanations do not convince anyone nor does it defend his God. Strangely enough he does not fail to stand with the suffering man. It is the failure of theodicy, a failure in thought and speech but not in activity. The divine escapes his language, or he never understands his God. What can be shown cannot be said. Language cannot represent. What expresses itself in language, we cannot express by means of language. Propositions show the logical form of reality. They display it. If only you do not try to utter what is unutterable then nothing gets lost. But the unutterable will be – unutterably – contained in what has been uttered! Language thus contains a dialectical tension between the expressible and the ineffable. The limits of language cannot be overcome but by poetic language which can insinuate or resonate the other worldly values. As a seeker of the truth of the mystery evil is revealed in the crucified who cried

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aloud on the cross, "My God, My God, why have you forsaken me". The world suffers from the absence of God. The word which became flesh lost his body. Mary Magdalene is seeking the body of the Lord ready to take it away. The Church lives to give body to Him. The Priests every day make His body, "This is my body." A body to enter history and make justice and love embody to serve God in man and in the world. A theodicy can be drawn from the cry of the cross and the solemn silence that haunts the world. The responsibility of the follower of God is to respond to the absence of the divine in the world afflicted by plagues.

The Christian response to plagues begins with some of Jesus's most famous teachings: "Do unto others as you would have them do unto you"; "Love your neighbour as yourself"; "Greater love has no man than this, that he should lay down his life for his friends." Put plainly, the Christian ethic in a time of plague considers that our own life must always be regarded as less important than that of our neighbour. During plague periods in the Roman Empire, Christians made a name for themselves. Historians have suggested that the terrible Antonine Plague of the 2nd century, which might have killed off a quarter of the Roman Empire, led to the spread of Christianity, as Christians cared for the sick and offered an spiritual model whereby plagues were

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not the work of angry and capricious deities but the product of a broken Creation in revolt against a loving God. But the more famous epidemic is the Plague of Cyprian, named after a bishop who gave a colourful account of this disease in his sermons. Probably a disease related to Ebola, the Plague of Cyprian helped set off the crisis of the Third Century in the Roman world. But it did something else, too: It triggered the explosive growth of Christianity. Cyprian's sermons told Christians not to grieve for plague victims (who live in heaven), but to redouble efforts to care for the living. His fellow bishop Dionysius described how Christians, "Heedless of danger ... took charge of the sick, attending to their every need." Nor was it just Christians who noted this reaction of Christians to the plague. A century later, the actively pagan Emperor Julian would complain bitterly of how "the Galileans" would care for even non-Christian sick people, while the Church historian Pontianus recounts how Christians ensured that "good was done to all men, not merely to the household of faith." I conclude with the words of Albert Camus in *The Plague*, "The plague bacillus never dies or disappears for good; ... it can lie dormant for years in furniture and linen-chests; ... it bides its time in bedrooms, cellars, trunks, and bookshelves; and ... perhaps the day would come when, for the bane and enlightening of men, it roused up its rats again and sent them forth to die in a happy city (TP, p. 252).

Reference

Camus, Albert. *The Plague*, London: Penguin Group, 1960 [1947].